

1 Thermochemical processing of boron-impregnated
2 cellulose insulation waste for upcycling to slow-release
3 boron fertilizers

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19

20 **Abstract**

21 Boron (B) fertilizers are essential for global crop production. Sustainable B use demands a higher efficiency
22 of B fertilizers through controlled B release and an enhanced B recycling from secondary sources, *e.g.* B-
23 impregnated cellulose fiber insulation (CFI) waste. In this study, thermochemical treatments based on
24 combustion and pyrolysis were investigated for processing CFI waste into a slow-release B fertilizer. Hot-
25 water extractions of obtained materials confirmed that slow-release properties were achieved, and
26 material characterization with XRD, FTIR and ¹¹B-NMR showed that these were largely the result of
27 formation of sparingly soluble Ca-B phases. A seedling toxicity test with fodder rape demonstrated the
28 benefit of this slow-release B in comparison with conventional soluble B to circumvent toxicity, suggesting
29 potential for B application via seed coatings. Finally, a fertilization trial with fodder rape and poppy seed
30 showed that most slow-release B compounds were equally effective as soluble B at recommended B
31 doses, while slow-release B can still benefit from reduced B leaching losses.

32

33 **Keywords**

34 Boron fertilizer; circular economy; construction waste; micronutrients; nutrient recycling; slow-release
35 fertilizer

36

38 1. Introduction

39 Boron (B) is an essential micronutrient for plants and has important functions in cell wall formation,
40 membrane integrity, pollination, and fruit development. Boron deficiency is mainly found in high-rainfall
41 regions around the world, such as northern Europe and eastern regions of North America and China
42 (Shorrocks, 1997). To overcome B deficiency in crop production systems, soluble B fertilizers are often
43 applied. These B fertilizers are derived from ore minerals (*e.g.* kernite, colemanite), largely originating
44 from mining activities in the USA, Turkey, South America, and China. In regions without large reserves, B
45 is considered a scarce resource and, therefore, borates have been recognized as a critical raw material for
46 the European Union (European Commission, 2017). In addition, the use of B heavily relies on the
47 availability of primary B, as the current global end-of-life recycling rate for B is below 1% (Henckens et al.,
48 2015). Against a background of finite primary B sources and risk for (local) scarcity of B resources, research
49 on a more sustainable use of B is gaining attention, focusing on more efficient B fertilizer application and
50 improved B recycling.

51 The use of conventional B fertilizers, *i.e.* highly-soluble compounds such as borax ($\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$), is
52 linked to limitations with respect to the efficiency of their application. First, B applied with soluble
53 fertilizers is vulnerable to leaching in soils, particularly in sandy soils with a low organic matter content
54 (Dhassi et al., 2019), which makes applied B unavailable for plant uptake. Hence, excessive B leaching,
55 linked to the high solubility of fertilizer B compounds, limits the B use efficiency of fertilizer applications
56 and results in dissipative losses of valuable B. Secondly, with soluble B application, special care should be
57 taken with regard to possible B toxicity in plants. Uptake of B by plants occurs mainly through passive
58 processes, making the uptake process less regulated (Tanaka and Fujiwara, 2008) and the B uptake by
59 plants highly correlated with B in soil solution (Keren et al., 1985). As a result of the passive B uptake and
60 a generally low plant B tolerance, there is only a narrow window between deficiency and toxicity for B.
61 Avoiding B toxicity with the use of soluble B fertilizer compounds becomes particularly challenging in plant

62 nutrition applications with placed B, *e.g.* borated granular fertilizers (Mortvedt and Osborn, 1965) and B
63 in seed coatings (Shabaz et al., 2015), where elevated local B concentrations in the soil solution can be
64 expected.

65 To address the challenges of B leaching and B toxicity, fertilizer research explored alternatives to
66 conventional soluble fertilizer compounds that can provide a slow release of B in soils. The use of
67 naturally-occurring B-rich minerals with reduced solubility, *e.g.* colemanite ($\text{Ca}_2\text{B}_6\text{O}_{11}\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and ulexite
68 ($\text{NaCaB}_5\text{O}_9\cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$), has been suggested (Broschat, 2008; Saleem et al., 2011) and various fertilizer
69 formulations have been developed, *e.g.* colemanite/ulexite co-granulated with muriate of potash (da Silva
70 et al., 2018), sintered colemanite pellets (Flores et al., 2006) and wax/sulfur-coated colemanite within a
71 pellet of diammonium phosphate (Samreen et al., 2021). In addition to naturally-occurring B minerals,
72 also synthetic slow-release B materials have been developed, *e.g.* superabsorbent formulations
73 embedding soluble B (Xie et al., 2011), B-loaded layered double hydroxide (de Castro et al., 2020, 2018),
74 zinc borates (Zheng et al., 2021), and BPO_4 (Abat et al., 2015a, 2015b, 2014). With the latter approach, it
75 was shown that sparingly soluble BPO_4 could be obtained from thermal treatment of H_3BO_3 and H_3PO_4 at
76 temperatures $>500^\circ\text{C}$.

77 Not only the development of more efficient B fertilizers from primary B sources, but also the recycling of
78 B from waste streams into compounds suitable for fertilizer applications can contribute to a more
79 sustainable B use. For example, B-rich fly ashes can serve as a B source for crops, yet high salinity and the
80 presence of other microelements could obstruct their direct use as B fertilizer (Manoharan et al., 2010).
81 Recently, end-of-life cellulose fiber insulation (CFI) was identified as a promising secondary source of B for
82 use in fertilizer applications (Duboc et al., 2019). In the production process of CFI materials, fibrous
83 cellulose-rich material derived from recycled paper waste is treated with boric acid or sodium borate
84 (typical application rates between 30-55 g B kg^{-1}), that act as fungicide, pest repellent and flame retardant
85 (Herrera, 2005; Hirata and Werner, 1987). The high solubility of B in CFI material was confirmed with hot-

86 water B extractions, while solubility slightly decreased after pyrolysis of the CFI material (Duboc et al.,
87 2019), In that study, the fertilizer potential of pyrolyzed CFI material was also demonstrated in a
88 greenhouse trial with rapeseed (*Brassica napus* L.) and sunflower (*Heliantus annuus* L.), where a
89 comparable plant B availability was obtained between pyrolyzed CFI material and conventional soluble
90 borax fertilizer although B uptake from pyrolyzed CFI tended to be lower. In a subsequent field trial study
91 with maize (*Zea mays* L.) and sunflower, pyrolyzed CFI biochar and borax fertilizer were compared for B
92 application (Duboc et al., 2021). The B uptake with CFI biochar was slightly below that with soluble borax
93 (10-20% lower). Overall, these two studies suggested that the solubility of B in CFI could be reduced via
94 thermal treatment, such as pyrolysis.

95 The recent developments in the area of slow-release B fertilizers and B recycling highlight a clear
96 opportunity for sustainable B use, *i.e.* the production of slow-release B fertilizer compounds derived from
97 B-rich waste materials. As such, the production of an enhanced-efficiency B fertilizer has the potential to
98 valorize B recycling from waste streams. Against this background, this study investigated the development
99 of a slow-release B fertilizer from CFI material using thermochemical treatments. For this, CFI material,
100 either or not pretreated with diluted H_3PO_4 , was exposed to combustion or pyrolysis treatments at varying
101 temperature. The H_3PO_4 treatment was included to promote slow B release properties through the
102 formation of BPO_4 (Abat et al., 2014). The slow-release properties of the obtained materials were
103 evaluated with sequential hot-water B extraction, and their B release properties substantiated via
104 material characterization (XRD, FTIR, ^{11}B -NMR). In a toxicity test, fodder rape seedling emergence and
105 growth was assessed at high B doses of prepared CFI materials and conventional B fertilizers (borax,
106 colemanite) to mimic a seed coating environment and assess the benefits of slow B release on averting
107 toxicity in the seedlings. Finally, in a fertilization trial with fodder rape and poppy seed, the plant B
108 availability from selected CFI fertilizers was compared to that of conventional soluble B fertilizers.

109

110 **2. Materials and methods**

111 **2.1. CFI materials and reference fertilizers**

112 The B-impregnated CFI material for this study was provided by Isocell GmbH (Neumarkt am Wallersee,
113 Austria). During the industrial production process, powdered borate salt was mixed homogeneously in
114 the cellulose material. The lightweight and fibrous CFI material was pelletized to facilitate the handling of
115 the material and the treatment in the furnace. For this, the fibrous CFI material was wetted with water at
116 250 mL kg⁻¹ material, left in a closed PE bag for 24 h to homogenize the humidity throughout the material,
117 and finally pelletized with a Kahl Presse 14-175 device. In addition to the regular CFI material, also a H₃PO₄-
118 impregnated CFI (P-CFI) was prepared. For this, batches of 300 g pelletized CFI material were sprayed with
119 378 mL of a 0.87 M H₃PO₄ solution (molar P/B ratio of 2) and incubated for 24 h at room temperature
120 (Abat et al., 2014). Subsequently, the P-CFI material was dried at 60 °C. Borax (Na₂B₄O₇·10H₂O, ≥99.5%,
121 obtained from *Sigma-Aldrich*) and colemanite (Ca₂B₆O₁₁·5H₂O, provided by *Colpaert NV*, Belgium) were
122 included as reference B fertilizer materials.

123

124 **2.2. Combustion and pyrolysis treatments**

125 The thermal treatments of the CFI and P-CFI materials were performed in a muffle furnace (Nabertherm
126 L15/11/B410). Both the combustion and pyrolysis treatments were performed at dwell temperatures of
127 500 °C, 575 °C, 650 °C, 725 °C, and 800 °C. For the combustion treatments, 200 g of CFI and P-CFI materials
128 were loaded into open steel trays (20 cm x 15 cm x 5 cm). The combustion was performed with a heating
129 ramp of 650 °C h⁻¹ and a dwell time of 4 h, while air was continuously flushed into the furnace (rate of 5 L
130 min⁻¹). For the pyrolysis treatments, the CFI and P-CFI materials were loaded into steel trays which were
131 then covered with a steel lid. The pyrolysis was performed with a heating ramp of 650 °C h⁻¹ and a dwell
132 time of 1 h, while the covered trays were continuously flushed inside with N₂ from 30 min before the start
133 of pyrolysis treatment (rate of 2 L min⁻¹). At the end of the dwell periods of the combustion and pyrolysis

134 treatments, the heating turned off and samples were only taken out of the N₂ atmosphere at
135 temperatures below 60 °C. When the samples were cooled down to room temperature, the weight of the
136 treated material was measured to determine the weight loss. Prior to characterization and further use of
137 the initial CFI material and the combustion/pyrolysis products, all materials were milled with a vibratory
138 ball mill (*Retsch MM 200*) using stainless steel grinding equipment to obtain a particle size <200 μm.

139

140 **2.3. Characterization of starting materials and thermochemical products**

141 Elemental analysis of the initial CFI and P-CFI materials was determined with inductively coupled plasma
142 optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES, Thermo Scientific iCAP 7000, and Optima 8300, Perkin Elmer Inc.,
143 Waltham/MA, USA) after digestion in boiling HNO₃ using a MARS 6 microwave digestion system (*CEM*).
144 The C/N content of the initial CFI and P-CFI materials and of the combustion and pyrolysis products was
145 determined with a vario MACRO cube (Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Langenselbold, Germany). The
146 CFI and P-CFI starting materials were characterized with thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, TA Instruments
147 Q500 V6.7 Build 203) in an air atmosphere and in a N₂ atmosphere, using a Pt pan with a 5 °C min⁻¹ heating
148 ramp to 800 °C. Also, the ash content of the CFI and P-CFI materials was determined in a furnace treatment
149 at 525 °C (ISO 1762). The crystallographic characteristics of the materials obtained from the
150 thermochemical treatments were investigated with powder X-ray diffraction (XRD), performed with a
151 Malvern PANalytical Empyrean diffractometer in transmission mode, using a PIXcel3D solid state detector
152 and Cu anode (Cu Kα1: 1.5406 Å; Cu Kα2: 1.5444 Å). The FTIR analysis of these materials was performed
153 with a Bruker IFS 66v/S spectrophotometer. Finally, solid-state ¹¹B NMR experiments were performed on
154 the initial CFI and P-CFI materials and a selection of treated samples using a Varian Inova spectrometer in
155 a wide-bore 11.7 T magnet at a frequency of 160.36 MHz. The reference was set with a NaBH₄ solution to
156 -42.06 ppm. Magic Angle Spinning (MAS) experiments were performed with a 4 mm Chemagnetics probe,
157 with a spinning speed of 15 kHz, and a single-pulse and acquisition experiment. The radiofrequency pulses

158 had a duration of 4.5 μ s and the signal was accumulated with 1024 scans, having a total experimental time
159 of 18 minutes per sample (the time for packing of the rotors has not been considered). The spectral
160 window was set to approximately 625 ppm and the FID acquisition time was 40 ms. The obtained NMR
161 signal was Fourier Transformed with 25 Hz of linear broadening as apodization to obtain the spectra of
162 the different samples.

163

164 **2.4. Hot-water B extraction**

165 Successive hot-water extractions were performed on the CFI and P-CFI starting materials, and on the
166 combustion and pyrolysis products. For this, 200 mg of each fertilizer material was weighted into 15-mL
167 polypropylene centrifuge tubes, to which 10 mL of water was added (liquid:solid ratio of 50 mL g⁻¹).
168 Subsequently, the centrifuge tubes were transferred to a shaking water bath (95 °C), in which the samples
169 were shaken for 10 min after reaching the water bath temperature (time for suspension to reach 95 °C:
170 5 min). After each extraction step, the extractant solution was separated from the fertilizer material via
171 centrifugation (3,000 g, 30 min) and decantation, after which fresh water was added for the subsequent
172 extraction step. Half of the extraction volumes were filtered (0.45 μ m, VWR) and analyzed with ICP-OES
173 (Optima 8300, Perkin Elmer Inc., Waltham/MA, USA) to determine the B concentration, while the
174 remaining unfiltered volume was used to measure the solution pH at room temperature.

175

176 **2.5. Seedling toxicity test**

177 In a seedling toxicity test with fodder rape seeds (*Brassica napus* cv. *Anarion*), the suitability of different
178 B fertilizers for use in seed coatings was examined by comparing borax, colemanite, CFI-575, CFI-800, P-
179 CFI-575 and P-CFI-800 ash samples. A sandy soil was sampled from Houthalen in Belgium (51°00'39" N,
180 5°27'11" E), and plastic trays were filled with 0.5 kg of this dry soil (properties in Table 1). To each soil,

181 Ca(OH)_2 slaked lime was added at a rate of 200 mg kg^{-1} soil to obtain a pH of 7.5. The B fertilizers were
182 mixed into the soil samples as powders at rates of 7.2 mg B kg^{-1} or $28.8 \text{ mg B kg}^{-1}$ soil. For borax, additional
183 B doses were included to obtain a toxicity response curve, with B rates up to $115.2 \text{ mg B kg}^{-1}$ soil. All
184 treatments were prepared in triplicate. Subsequently, a diluted nutrient solution was added to the trays
185 to reach 80% of the water holding capacity (WHC) of the soil (180 mL kg^{-1} soil) and to supply 35.0 mg N
186 kg^{-1} , 7.4 mg P kg^{-1} , $3.0 \text{ mg Ca kg}^{-1}$, $16.5 \text{ mg K kg}^{-1}$, 3.5 mg S kg^{-1} and $0.9 \text{ mg Mg kg}^{-1}$ (modified from Middleton
187 and Toxopeus, 1973). The wetted soils were incubated at $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the dark for 24 h, after which 100 fodder
188 rape seeds were planted evenly over the soil surface in each tray (2 mm depth). The trays were installed
189 in a growth chamber with a day/night regime of 16 h light ($25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and 8 h darkness ($20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), a light intensity
190 of $650 \text{ mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ during the day, and a relative humidity of 75%. Water losses were corrected
191 four times every day using a fine spray of deionized water. After 7 days of growth, top-view pictures were
192 taken of the seedlings in the trays, from which the percentage of vegetation coverage was determined
193 with image analysis software (*GIMP 2.10*) (Abat et al., 2015b). Subsequently, the seedlings were harvested
194 by cutting them 0.5 cm above the soil surface (removing remaining soil on the seedlings), after which the
195 plant material was dried at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 48 h. The dried plant material was digested in boiling HNO_3 using a
196 MARS 6 microwave digestion system (CEM) to determine the B content with Inductive Coupled Plasma
197 Mass Spectroscopy (ICP-MS, Agilent 7700x, Agilent technologies). The remaining soil in the trays, still at
198 80% WHC, was subjected to pore water extraction using the double-chamber centrifugation method
199 (Fraters et al., 2017). The B concentration in the recovered pore water samples was determined with ICP-
200 OES.

201

202

203 Table 1: Selected physicochemical properties of soil from Houthalen, Belgium (51°00'39" N, 5°27'11" E).

Soil location	Soil type ^a	Sand ^b (%)	Silt ^b (%)	Clay ^b (%)	pH (CaCl ₂) ^c	C/N ^d	Org C ^d (%)	CEC ^e (cmol _c kg ⁻¹)	FC ^f (mL kg ⁻¹)	Oxalate extraction ^g (mg kg ⁻¹)		Exchangeable cations (cmol _c kg ⁻¹)
										Al	Fe	Al
Houthalen, Belgium	Haplic Podzol	86	9	5	3.4, 7.4 ^h	22.8	1.86	1.9	225	199	492	1.0

204 ^a Major soil groups WRB 2015; ^b Texture of acid soil determined by pipette method; ^c pH (1:5 S:L) in 0.01 M CaCl₂ (acid soil pH was
 205 limed to pH 7.4 for the fertilization trial); ^d C/N and organic C as % of total soil mass determined by the combustion method; ^e
 206 Cation exchange capacity (CEC) was determined in a 0.0166 M cobalt hexamine (Cohex) extract (ISO, 2007), as the difference
 207 between total Co added and Co measured in the extract with ICP-OES; ^f Field capacity (FC) determined through the glistening
 208 effect; ^g Ammonium oxalate extractable Fe, Al and P, ^h After application of Ca(OH)₂ at 200 mg kg⁻¹.

209

210 2.6. Fertilization trial

211 In a greenhouse fertilization trial with poppy seed (*Papaver somniferum* cv. Edel-Rot) and fodder rape
 212 (*Brassica napus* cv. Liform), the plant B availability was compared between prepared CFI B fertilizers (CFI-
 213 575, CFI-800, P-CFI-575 and P-CFI-800 ash samples) and conventional B fertilizers (borax and colemanite).
 214 The growth medium used in this trial was a mixture of 67 wt% soil (properties in Table 2) and 33 wt% sand
 215 (0.3 – 1 mm). Two kg of soil/sand mixture were added to each pot. The B fertilizers were applied by mixing
 216 the dry fertilizer powders into the growth medium at a rate of 0.385 mg B kg⁻¹, which corresponds to the
 217 Austrian fertilizer recommendation of 1 kg B ha⁻¹ (BMLFUW, 2017), assuming an incorporation depth of
 218 20 cm and a soil bulk density of 1300 kg m⁻³. In addition to the different B fertilizer treatments, also a
 219 control treatment was included without B application. All treatments were prepared in quadruplicate. The
 220 soil water content was maintained at 70% of the maximum water holding capacity of the soil/sand mixture
 221 during the full growth period. Ten seeds of poppy seed or eight seeds of fodder rape were planted in the
 222 respective pots and thinned to four plants at 15 days after sowing (DAS). Growth conditions included
 223 humidity of 60%, day/night cycle of 16/8 h, with day/night temperature of 25/15 °C. On top of the sunlight
 224 in the greenhouse, artificial lighting provided an additional photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) of
 225 100-200 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹. Nutrient solution (100 mL) was added at planting and four more times until 42 DAS

226 (fodder rape) and 55 DAS (poppy seed). The solution was adapted from Middleton and Toxopeus (1973)
 227 and contained 4000 mg L⁻¹ NH₄NO₃, 800 mg L⁻¹ NaH₂PO₄·2H₂O, 400 mg L⁻¹ Ca(H₂PO₄)₂·H₂O, 1470 mg L⁻¹
 228 K₂SO₄, 444 mg L⁻¹ MgSO₄·7H₂O, 360 mg L⁻¹ CaCO₃, 7.2 mL mL⁻¹ 1 mol L⁻¹ HCl, 8 mg L⁻¹ CuCl₂, 30 mg L⁻¹
 229 MnCl₂·4H₂O, 1 mg L⁻¹ (NH₄)Mo₇O₂₄·4H₂O, 10 mg L⁻¹ ZnCl₂, 20 mg L⁻¹ Fe-EDDHA (5.7 wt% Fe). In total, the
 230 following amounts of nutrients were added to each pot: 706 mg N, 128 mg P, 330 mg K, 164 mg S,
 231 22 mg Mg, 104 mg Ca, 1.90 mg Cu kg⁻¹, 4.16 mg Mn kg⁻¹, 0.29 mg Mo kg⁻¹, 2.4 mg Zn kg⁻¹, 0.57 mg Fe kg⁻¹.
 232 The fodder rape shoots were harvested at 55 DAS and the poppy seed shoots at 68 DAS, by cutting the
 233 shoots at 2 cm above the soil surface. Subsequently, the shoots were rinsed with deionized water and
 234 dried for 96 h at 65 °C. The shoot dry matter yield was determined, and the plant material was milled in a
 235 GRINDOMIX GM 200 knife mill (Retsch GmbH, Haan, Germany). The B content of the shoots was
 236 determined with ICP-OES (Optima 8300, Perkin Elmer Inc., Waltham/MA, USA) after digestion of the
 237 milled plant material in HNO₃/H₂O₂ using a microwave digestion system.

238

239 Table 2: Selected physicochemical properties of the soil from Austria used in the greenhouse fertilization trial.

pH (CaCl ₂) ^a	C/N ^b	Org. C ^b (%)	Inorg. C ^b (%)	CEC ^c (cmol _c kg ⁻¹)	CAL-P ^d (mg P kg ⁻¹)	CAL-K ^d (mg K kg ⁻¹)	Hot H ₂ O B ^e (mg B kg ⁻¹)	FC ^f (mL kg ⁻¹)
6.4	12	1.65	0	8.7	67.7	192	0.42	358

240 ^a pH (1:2.5 S:L) in 0.01 M CaCl₂; ^b Determined by dry combustion in a soliTOC (Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Langenselbold,
 241 Germany). Increasing temperature steps (400, 600 and 900 °C) were used according to DIN19539. Organic C was calculated as
 242 the sum of C combusted at 400 °C and 600 °C; ^c Extracted with 0.01 mol L⁻¹ BaCl₂ (ÖNORM L 1096) expressed as total charge of
 243 extracted Ca, K, Mg, Na and Al; ^d Calcium Acetate Lactate method (ÖNORM L 1087); ^e Hot Water Boron Extraction (ÖNORM L
 244 1090); ^f Field capacity (FC) determined through the glistening effect.

245

246 **3. Results and discussion**

247 **3.1. Characterization of the CFI materials before and after thermochemical treatment**

248 An in-depth characterization of the CFI starting material was performed. The elemental analysis of the CFI
249 material revealed a B content of 5.27 mg g⁻¹ (Table 3) and a total C content of 35.2% (Table 4). The
250 presence of cellulose was evidenced by the characteristic IR bands at 667 cm⁻¹, 918 cm⁻¹, 1002 cm⁻¹, 1151
251 cm⁻¹ and 1414 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 1) (Siddhanta et al., 2009) and XRD reflections at 16° and 22° 2θ (Fig. 2). The CFI
252 material also had a relatively high Ca content of 43.5 mg g⁻¹, which was attributed to the presence of
253 calcite (CaCO₃), as shown by characteristic IR bands (*e.g.* at 713 cm⁻¹, 876 cm⁻¹ and 1432 cm⁻¹) (Fig. 1) and
254 XRD reflections (*e.g.* at 29° 2θ) (Fig. 2) of the CFI material. The presence of a prominent calcite phase in
255 the CFI material was likely due the fact that lime is often used in paper production as a whitening additive.
256 Other mineral phases in the CFI material included quartz, gypsum, and kaolinite (Fig. 2). The P-CFI material
257 had a similar elemental and mineralogical composition as the CFI material, yet had a higher P content
258 (37.5 mg P g⁻¹), a higher ash content (28.6% for P-CFI, 25.8% for CFI) and slightly lower C content (Table
259 4). The lower C content of the P-CFI was attributed to loss of CO₂ as a result of calcite dissolution (and
260 subsequent CO₂ gas formation) during the acid H₃PO₄ treatment, which was also confirmed by XRD and
261 FTIR of the P-CFI material.

262 Table 3: Elemental composition of the CFI material.

Element	Al	B	C	Ca	Fe	K	Mg	N	Na	P	S
<i>mg g⁻¹</i>	5.31	5.27	351.8	43.5	0.42	1.76	5.7	1.41	0.81	0.10	5.77

263

264

265 Table 4: The total C content (organic C and inorganic C) of the starting material and the thermochemically treated
 266 materials, presented in wt%.

Temperature (°C)	Weight loss (wt%)			
	Combustion		Pyrolysis	
	CFI	P-CFI	CFI	P-CFI
-	35.2	32.4	35.2	32.4
500	5.4	2.8	45.6	45.0
575	5.0	3.2	44.3	40.1
650	1.3	0.8	40.4	40.0
725	0.2	0.0	43.5	39.1
800	0.0	0.0	42.4	38.7

267

268

269 Fig. 1: The FTIR spectra of the starting materials and the thermochemically treated materials.

270

271 Fig. 2: The XRD patterns of the starting materials and the thermochemically treated materials.

272

273 The recorded weight losses of the thermal treatments of the CFI and P-CFI materials under oxidative and
 274 inert atmosphere in the furnace were well in line with the TGA measurements in corresponding conditions
 275 (Fig. 3 and in supplementary material). Three main processes for weight loss could be derived from the
 276 TGA plots. First, evaporation of physically and chemically bound water occurred up to a temperature of
 277 250 °C. Secondly, weight losses at elevated temperatures were also attributed to volatilization due to
 278 cellulose decomposition, which for the CFI material occurred at temperatures above 250 °C and for P-CFI
 279 at temperatures above 220 °C (Karacan and Soy, 2013). The combustion treatments, on the one hand,
 280 resulted in the removal of the organic phase (cellulose), which was nearly completed at 500 °C, the lowest
 281 temperature tested in the furnace (Table 4, Fig. 1, Fig. 2). With the pyrolysis treatments, on the other
 282 hand, a large part of the organic C was maintained in the material (Table 4), which transformed into
 283 graphene phases at temperatures above 725 °C (Fig. 1, Fig. 2) (Li and Chen, 2018). Thirdly, thermal
 284 decomposition of calcite occurred at ~650 °C (Fig. 1, Fig. 2), which was more pronounced for the CFI than
 285 for the P-CFI material, since the CFI material contained more calcite in comparison with the P-CFI material.

286 As a result of combustion at temperatures above 725 °C, and thus volatilization of both organic and
 287 inorganic C, the total C content of the obtained materials obtained was close to zero (Table 4). Other
 288 important points of the material characterization were (i) the loss of a minor kaolinite ($\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_4$)
 289 phase at temperatures below 500 °C, (ii) the formation of a β -tricalcium phosphate ($\beta\text{-Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$) phase in
 290 P-CFI material at 650 °C or higher, as shown by the characteristic IR bands at 955 cm^{-1} , 988 cm^{-1} and
 291 1120 cm^{-1} and the XRD pattern (Berzina-Cimdina and Borodajenko, 2012), and (iii) the presence of quartz
 292 (SiO_2) and anatase (TiO_2) phases in all treated materials, which demonstrated the inert nature of these
 293 phases (Fig. 2).

294
 295 Fig. 3: The TGA plots of the CFI and P-CFI materials in air atmosphere and in N_2 atmosphere (full lines), presented
 296 with the recorded weight loss during the corresponding thermochemical treatments (dotted lines).

297
 298 The characterization with FTIR and XRD showed that the thermochemical treatments of the CFI material
 299 also affected the speciation of B in the obtained materials. In addition, ^{11}B -NMR analysis was used to
 300 derive the B coordination in the B-containing phases of the different treated materials, *i.e.* to distinguish
 301 between planar triangular (denoted as BO_3 , chemical shift ranging between -5 ppm and 5 ppm) and

302 tetrahedral B (denoted as BO_4 , chemical shift ranging between 5 ppm and 20 ppm) species (Fig. 4)
303 (Edwards et al., 2014).

304 For both the CFI and the P-CFI starting materials, a mixed BO_3/BO_4 speciation was observed and crystalline
305 B phases were absent. With the combustion of CFI material at the lowest tested temperatures, there was
306 no evidence for significant changes in the B speciation, and the mixed BO_3/BO_4 speciation of the CFI
307 material was maintained (Fig. 4). However, CFI combustion at 650 °C and 725 °C resulted in the formation
308 of a takedaite ($\text{Ca}_3\text{B}_2\text{O}_6$, BO_3 coordination) phase, as shown by the characteristic IR band at 723 cm^{-1} and
309 XRD pattern (Fig. 1, Fig. 2) (Frost et al., 2014), which likely was the result of the thermal decomposition of
310 CaCO_3 to CaO and the subsequent reaction between CaO and B_2O_3 . With the combustion of CFI at 800 °C,
311 the takedaite phase was less pronounced and crystalline B was also found in shimazakiite ($\text{Ca}_2\text{B}_2\text{O}_5$, BO_3
312 coordination) and fabianite ($\text{CaB}_3\text{O}_5(\text{OH})$, BO_4 coordination) phases, with both NMR and FTIR (*e.g.* B-O
313 stretching vibration of BO_4 at 1110 cm^{-1}) showing an enhanced BO_4 speciation (Jun et al., 1995).

314 In contrast to combustion of CFI material, the combustion of P-CFI material resulted in the formation of
315 crystalline B phases at the lower tested temperatures (500 °C and 575 °C), *i.e.* takedaite and BPO_4 (BO_4
316 coordination) phases, and BO_4 coordination was most pronounced in these obtained materials (*e.g.* BPO_4).
317 Indeed, the formation of BPO_4 could occur at temperatures from 500 °C onwards (Abat et al., 2014), while
318 also takedaite in P-CFI material could be formed at lower temperatures than in CFI material as result of
319 the acid H_3PO_4 treatment of P-CFI material dissolving calcite and allowing Ca-B reactions during
320 combustion. Also at temperatures above 650 °C, combustion of P-CFI resulted in takedaite and BPO_4
321 formation, with NMR suggesting a pronounced BO_3 coordination (*e.g.* takedaite).

322 With the pyrolysis of CFI material, takedaite was formed at 650 °C, which also remained a pronounced
323 crystalline B phase at higher temperatures. The latter was also in line with pronounced BO_3 coordination

324 at 800 °C. Finally, B speciation obtained with the pyrolysis of P-CFI was similar with that of P-CFI
325 combustion.

326

327 Fig. 4: The ^{11}B NMR spectra of the starting materials and selected thermochemically treated materials.

328

329 3.2. Hot-water B extraction

330 Hot-water extractions were performed to assess the solubility of B in the initial CFI and P-CFI materials
331 and in the products of the thermochemical treatments (Fig. 5). With this sequential extraction approach,
332 no replicate treatments were performed and, therefore, the interpretation of the results was based on
333 the regular effects of temperature and extraction series. A high B solubility was obtained for the initial CFI
334 material in the first extraction step (77%), which was in line with earlier results (Duboc et al., 2019). After
335 five extraction steps, a cumulative B extraction of 87% from CFI was obtained. The pH of the CFI extraction
336 solutions was between 7.1 and 8.1. Extraction of the prepared P-CFI material demonstrated high B
337 solubility, and a cumulative B extraction of 90% was obtained. The H_3PO_4 treatment of CFI reduced the
338 pH of the first extraction to 5.8, as a result of the dissolution of the pH-buffering calcite phase. The

339 solubility of the reference compound colemanite was in line with earlier reported values (Abat et al.,
340 2014), with extract B concentrations ranging between 232 and 286 mg L⁻¹ and pH values of the extract
341 solutions between 9.4 and 9.5 (supplementary material).

342 The hot-water extraction of the thermochemically-treated materials showed the effects of the H₃PO₄
343 pretreatment and the thermal treatment conditions (atmosphere and temperature) on the solubility of B
344 (Fig. 5). Combustion of CFI material at temperatures below 650 °C only slightly affected B solubility.
345 However, at combustion temperatures of 650 °C and above, B solubility decreased strongly, yielding
346 extract B concentrations below 30 mg L⁻¹. With subsequent extractions, B concentrations further
347 decreased to values below 15 mg L⁻¹. This reduced B solubility obtained for combustion at 650 °C and
348 above can be linked to the formation of a sparingly soluble takedaite phase, following the thermal
349 decomposition of calcite and the subsequent production of reactive CaO at this temperature (Fig. 2). Also
350 after CFI combustion at 800 °C and the formation of a shimazakiite phase, a low B solubility was
351 maintained. This reduced solubility of B from Ca-B compounds (*e.g.* takedaite) was confirmed in earlier
352 studies focusing on B recovery from liquid waste streams via Ca-B precipitation (Ezechi et al., 2015; Vu et
353 al., 2018). The thermal decomposition of calcite strongly changed the pH of the extraction solution, with
354 the pH of CFI extracts treated below a temperature of 650 °C being at least 2 pH units below those treated
355 at 650 °C and above. The high pH of the extract solutions with CFI treated at high temperatures, reaching
356 values up to pH 12, was the result of the strongly alkaline character of CaO and its reaction products, *e.g.*
357 takedaite.

358 In contrast with the CFI material, the combustion of P-CFI material at lower temperatures (500 °C, 575 °C)
359 did result in a noticeably reduced B solubility, likely as result of a partial formation of takedaite and BPO₄.
360 Next to takedaite, also BPO₄ is a sparingly soluble B phase (Abat et al., 2014). With the combustion at
361 800 °C (P-CFI-800), the lowest cumulative B extraction of all tested treatments was obtained (14%). The
362 pH values of the extraction solutions of the P-CFI combustion products were significantly lower than those

363 of the corresponding CFI combustion treatments. This was linked to the fact that CaCO_3 and CaO phases,
364 both with dominant acid-base properties, were present at much lower quantities in the P-CFI materials in
365 comparison with the CFI materials.

366 The effect of the temperature and the H_3PO_4 pretreatment with the pyrolysis treatments followed the
367 same trends that were obtained with the combustion, yet generally higher B solubilities were obtained
368 with pyrolysis. With the pyrolysis of CFI material also a drop in B solubility was obtained with pyrolysis at
369 $650\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, yet the reduction was not to the same extent as with the combustion treatment and B
370 concentrations in the first extraction of all pyrolysed CFI materials remained above 60 mg L^{-1} . While also
371 a takedaite phase was identified in CFI pyrolysis products at $650\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and higher, it was expected that the
372 amount of takedaite formed was limited in the pyrolysis products in comparison with the combustion
373 products, possibly because the organic char matrix in the pyrolysis samples obstructs the formation of
374 new B phases with lower solubility, *e.g.* takedaite. The pH values of the extraction solutions with pyrolysis
375 products were very similar with those from corresponding combustion products.

376

377

378 Fig. 5: The cumulative B extraction from initial and thermochemically treated materials (CFI and P-CFI), the B
 379 concentration in the extraction solutions and the pH of the extraction solutions, as obtained from the sequential
 380 hot-water extraction.

381

382 3.3. Seedling toxicity trial

383 The suitability of selected CFI and P-CFI combustion products for use in seed coatings was assessed in a
 384 seedling toxicity trial with fodder rape. At elevated B application doses that simulated local seed coating
 385 conditions, the CFI fertilizers were compared with conventional B compounds (borax, colemanite) in terms
 386 of obtained seedling vegetated area, seedling dry matter yield (DMY), seedling B content, and soil solution
 387 B concentration (Fig. 6).

388 First, the seedling response to soluble B (borax) was investigated over a broad range of B application
389 doses, from a control treatment (no B addition) to 155.2 mg B kg⁻¹ (Fig. 6, left). The response pattern
390 showed that borax application at a dose of 7.2 mg B kg⁻¹ increased the vegetated area and DMY in
391 comparison with the control treatment. This positive effect on seed emergence and seedling development
392 was also shown by Rehman et al. (2022). However, with borax application above 7.2 mg B kg⁻¹, increasing
393 doses decreased the vegetated area and DMY as a result of B toxicity, resulting in the complete absence
394 of germination at a dose of 115.2 mg B kg⁻¹. Earlier work reports that a reduction in DMY occurs from leaf
395 B concentrations of 0.30 mg g⁻¹ onwards, while in the current experiment this reduction was shown for
396 plant B concentrations above 0.52 mg B g⁻¹ (Bergmann, 1993).

397 The different fertilizers were then compared at two different B doses, *i.e.* one dose at which soluble B
398 application was beneficial for seedling development (7.2 mg B kg⁻¹) and one dose at which soluble B
399 application clearly became toxic (28.8 mg B kg⁻¹) (Fig. 6, right). At the dose of 7.2 mg B kg⁻¹, no differences
400 in vegetated area, DMY and soil solution pH were obtained between the fertilizers, yet a reduced plant B
401 content and B concentration in the soil solution of particularly the CFI-800 and P-CFI-800 materials hinted
402 at a delayed B release in comparison with the soluble compounds. For the dose of 28.8 mg B kg⁻¹, high
403 values in vegetated area and DMY were very well maintained for the slow-release compound P-CFI-800
404 and, to a slightly lesser extent, also for the CFI-800 compound. For CFI-575 and P-CFI-575 at the same B
405 dose, however, the vegetated area and DMY were strongly reduced, to values not significantly different
406 to those obtained with borax and colemanite. This indicated the high availability of B from these last two
407 CFI-derived compounds, resulting in B toxicity at this high B dose. The trend in the soil solution B
408 concentration and plant B content also very well supported these observations of seedling development.

409

410 Fig. 6: The vegetated area of the seedlings, the dry matter yield (DMY), the soil solution pH and the plant B content
 411 of the B fodder rape toxicity trial, presented for the borax response treatment with 0 – 115.2 mg B kg⁻¹ doses (left)
 412 and the fertilizer comparison at doses of 7.2 and 28.8 mg B kg⁻¹ (right). Error bars represent the standard error (n=3),

413 and different letters above the bars indicate significant differences between the treatments of the same B dose
414 (Tukey HSD test, $\alpha < 0.05$).

415

416 **3.4. Fertilization trial**

417 In the fertilization experiment, the fodder rape plants were harvested at 55 DAS. At this time, the fodder
418 rape water consumption was so high that the water reservoir of the 2-kg pots was emptied daily. We
419 decided to harvest the plants earlier than planned in order to avoid water scarcity to distort the
420 experimental results. The poppy seed plants were harvested at 68 DAS, when B deficiency symptoms
421 (shoot tip necroses, deformed young leaves, see supplementary material) were clearly visible.

422 Dry matter yield was on average 15.2 ± 0.9 for poppy seed and 17.5 ± 1.3 g pot⁻¹ for fodder rape plants
423 (Fig. 7). The effect of B deficiency on poppy seed growth was non-significant (max. 11 % increase between
424 control and P-CFI-800, with $p = 0.24$). However, if we had allowed the poppy seed plants to grow longer,
425 significant differences in biomass production clearly would have been expected. No effect of B supply on
426 dry matter yield of fodder rape as observed.

427 In contrast to the weak effect on DMY, the B content in shoot tissue increased by a factor of two to three
428 in fertilized treatments compared to the unfertilized control treatments. It ranged from 9.6 to 32.2 $\mu\text{g B g}^{-1}$
429 ¹ in poppy seed and from 11.2 to 31.3 $\mu\text{g B g}^{-1}$ in fodder rape. Accordingly, differences in B uptake mostly
430 followed B content and ranged from 0.135 to 0.5 mg B pot⁻¹ for poppy seed and from 0.2 to 0.54 mg B
431 pot⁻¹ for fodder rape (Fig. 7).

432 The average B concentrations in the shoots of the unfertilized plants was in the range of B deficiency
433 thresholds reported in literature (Asad et al., 2002; Bell, 1997; Huang et al., 1996). Although the effect of
434 B deficiency on DMY could not be detected on fodder rape at the time of harvest and was only marginal
435 in poppy seed, B deficiency was clearly identified by visual observation of the poppy seed plants. The most

436 evident symptom was shoot tip necrosis and deformed young leaves (supplementary material).
437 Furthermore, control poppy seed plants also looked smaller compared to the fertilized ones, which – at
438 least partly – appears to be due to less upright standing leaves than in the B-fertilized pots (supplementary
439 material). A possible explanation could be that plants had a weaker cell wall structure induced by B
440 deficiency which prevented a more upright posture (Goldbach and Wimmer, 2007).

441 In both crops, B content with P-CFI-800 was lower by 15 to 30 % compared to the other treatments,
442 whereby the difference was more pronounced with the poppy seed. Although it was less soluble than the
443 other fertilizers, P-CFI-800 provided enough B to alleviate B deficiency during the fertilization experiment.
444 This was in line with our other experiments on solubility and seedling toxicity and demonstrates that this
445 material has a high potential as a slow-release B fertilizer.

446

447

448 Fig. 7: The dry matter yield (DMY), the B content and the B uptake of the poppy seed and fodder rape shoots in the
 449 fertilization trial with different B fertilizer treatments (control without B, reference B fertilizers, CFI ash materials).
 450 Error bars represent the standard modelled error (n=4, except fodder rape control: n=3), and different letters above
 451 the bars indicate significant differences between the treatments (Tukey test, $\alpha < 0.05$).

452

453 **4. Conclusions**

454 In this study we have shown the potential of thermochemical processing of B-impregnated CFI to produce
455 a secondary slow-release B fertilizer. The effect of the initial material composition (mainly CaCO_3 content),
456 the thermal process parameters (mainly temperature) and the H_3PO_4 pretreatment on the speciation and
457 behavior of B in the treated CFI products was described in detail. Changes in B speciation from H_2O -soluble
458 H_3BO_3 to Ca-borates such as takedaite, sibirskite/shimazakiite and fabianite started at 650°C , and was
459 linked to reduced solubility. The obtained slow B release properties of the materials reduced seedling B
460 toxicity, while the products still provided enough B to alleviate B deficiency in the pot experiment.
461 Dissolution of CaCO_3 with the H_3PO_4 pretreatment allowed similar phase transformation from 500°C
462 onwards – since CaCO_3 did not need to first be thermally decomposed – while BPO_4 was also identified.
463 In terms of usability and performance, particularly regarding seedling toxicity, the CFI materials treated at
464 800°C (CFI-800 and P-CFI-800) outperformed not only the conventional water-soluble borax fertilizer (as
465 was expected) but also colemanite, which is sometimes used as a slow-release B fertilizer. Therefore, our
466 findings are highly relevant in a global context in which increasing resource use efficiency is paramount.
467 Further research and applications should build upon these results, by *e.g.* testing of coated seeds,
468 assessing B leaching and residual fertilization effects. Moreover, our results may also be useful to process
469 other secondary or primary B resources to slow-release fertilizers.

470

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482

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